

Assessing the changes in thermal and catalytic pyrolysis of lignocellulose when shifting from batch to continuous biomass feeding modes

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Abstract

Lignocellulosic biomass pyrolysis has been earlier studied in a large variety of reaction systems. However, there is a lack of information on the effects of passing from batch to continuous feeding mode (BM vs CM) despite being a necessary step in the scaling up of the process. In this sense, the main aim of this work is to conduct a comparative study of lignocellulosic biomass pyrolysis using the same reactor but varying the biomass feeding methods under thermal and catalytic conditions and different thermal zone temperatures (350 and 500 °C). Under thermal conditions, significant differences have been observed between both feeding systems. When operating in CM, the production of char decreases, particularly at 500 °C, from 27.3 to 18.9 wt% while the generation of gases increases. This can be attributed to the differences in the feeding mode since the CM allows a higher biomass heating rate, resulting in a more efficient lignocellulose decomposition. On the other hand, the balance between the higher residence time and the lower concentration of the vapours reduces the occurrence of secondary charring reactions. Consequently, the share of water in the liquid fraction diminishes in CM, although only a notable increase of bio-oil* (bio-oil in water-free basis) is observed at 500 °C (39.9 vs 45.0 wt%). The bio-oil* molecular composition is also modified by this shifting, leading to higher sugars and oxygenated-aromatics in the CM reactor at 500 °C. The different operation modes also affect the interaction between the vapours and the catalyst when the n-ZSM-5 is introduced into the reactor. The vapours are more diluted in CM in comparison with the batch one, allowing a more progressive and efficient catalytic conversion. As a result, less coke is deposited over the zeolite catalyst leading to an enhanced production of aromatic hydrocarbons, achieving yields of ca. 7.6 wt%.

Keywords

Lignocellulose pyrolysis; Continuous reactor; Batch reactor; ZSM-5; Aromatics

1. Introduction

The environmental and energy crisis, resulting from the excessive use of fossil fuels, has stressed the need for a fast transition towards the use of renewable resources for the sustainable production of energy and chemicals. Lignocellulosic biomass, such as forestry and agricultural residue, is a cost-effective alternative to obtain a wide range of carbon-based materials [1–3]. Pyrolysis stands out as one of the most promising alternatives to convert lignocellulose into valuable products due to its simplicity and versatility to admit different organic residues as feedstock [4,5]. During the pyrolysis process, the thermal decomposition of the lignocellulosic biopolymers (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin) occurs at temperatures ranging from 300 to 700 °C under an O₂-free atmosphere, yielding three main products: a gaseous phase mainly composed by CO and CO₂, a carbonaceous solid known as biochar and a liquid bio-oil, considered a precursor for biofuels and bio-based chemicals production [6,7]. However, the pyrolysis bio-oil is mainly composed of oxygenated organic compounds (carboxylic acids, aldehydes, ketones, ethers, esters, sugars, furans, phenols, and lignocellulose oligomers) and water. Consequently, the pyrolysis bio-oil is highly acidic, viscous, and unstable, resulting in low heating value, which limits its long-term storage and direct use as fuel [8,9].

The utilization of a catalyst during the pyrolysis of lignocellulose can upgrade the bio-oil properties, improving its stability, handling and content in added-value compounds such as phenolic or aromatic hydrocarbons [2,10,11]. For this process, known as catalytic pyrolysis, a wide variety of materials have been investigated, including activated carbons to boost the production of phenolic derivatives [4,12,13], metal oxides to promote the bio-oil deoxygenation [4,14], or acid solids to produce aromatic hydrocarbons [15,16]. In this context, zeolites are considered promising materials since their acidic and textural properties promote both deoxygenation and aromatization reactions, leading to a very high selectivity towards valuable

monoaromatic hydrocarbons. However, they also promote severe cracking reactions and coke formation, reducing both bio-oil* yield and catalyst lifetime [15].

Despite the huge potential of the catalytic pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass using zeolites, most of the research reported in the literature on this topic has been based on experimental data obtained in lab-scale batch reactors. These types of reactors provide valuable information to understand the chemical transformations that occur during the pyrolysis process, to compare the behaviour of different catalytic systems as well as optimize the operating conditions. However, these results cannot be extrapolated on a large scale due to the lack of correspondence between the results obtained in lab-scale batch reactors and those operating in continuous mode due to the differences in the feeding and heating rates as well as in the residence time of both solid and pyrolysis vapours, which significantly affect the product distribution and composition [17–19]. In addition, batch-type reactors do not provide any information about the deactivation and durability of the catalyst, which is a key parameter to evaluate the scale-up of the process [20]. The literature on continuous pyrolysis focus on reactors that are not equivalent to batch ones, such as fluidized bed [19,21], conical spouted bed [22,23], and screw reactor [18], while the direct comparison between the different reactor's operation mode has been rarely explored. Moreover, due to the operation challenges and the difficult recovery of all products, most studies lack comprehensive quantification, e.g. the calculation of yields to close mass balances and the full characterization of all pyrolysis products [17,20].

In this context, this work investigates how the shifting from a batch to a continuous biomass feeding mode affects both the distribution and composition of the pyrolysis products. The interest of the continuous system relies on the possibility of performing in situ studies on the autocatalytic properties of the biochar fraction and on the catalyst deactivation along the time on stream, both aspects being essential for the scale up of this technology. For that, the catalytic

pyrolysis of a forestry residue (oak woodchips) has been evaluated in a lab-scale fixed-bed reactor that can operate in both batch (BM) and continuous mode (CM), using a commercial n-ZSM-5 zeolite as a catalyst. All of the pyrolysis products have been quantified and extensively characterized in terms of molecular and elemental composition. The results obtained evidence that the distribution of the products is strongly affected by the operation mode, due to the changes that occurred in the biomass heating rate and concentration and residence time of the gases/vapours produced in both thermal and catalytic zones of the reaction system.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental setup

In this work, the thermal and catalytic pyrolysis of oak woodchips were studied by evaluating both continuous and batch operation modes. The experimental configurations used for this study, represented in Fig. 1-A and B, share the same reactor and differ only in the biomass feeding system, which allows an exhaustive comparison between both pyrolysis configurations. It consists of a stainless-steel downdraft reactor (25.4 x 600 mm) equipped with a heating system divided into two sections: the thermal zone, where the biomass is thermally decomposed, and the catalytic zone, where vapours generated during pyrolysis come into contact with the catalyst bed. Two electric furnaces are used to heat both zones independently, monitoring the internal temperatures using two K-type thermocouples. The reactor pressure was monitored using a Swagelok PGI pressure gauge (0 – 2.5 bar) with a resolution of 100 mbar, placed upstream of the reactor, not detecting any pressure drop during the experiments above this value.

In the case of the continuous configuration, the feeding system consists of a screw feeder (PID Eng&Tech, Spain) which is used to introduce into the reactor the selected biomass flow of 5 g/h. The gas flow is regulated with two mass flow controllers (Bronkhorst, El-Flow) to feed 100 ml/min of N₂, which is used as both purge and sweep gas. The biomass feeding starts after reaching an O₂-free atmosphere as well as the desired temperatures in the pyrolysis system.

Once inside the reactor, the biomass is rapidly decomposed in the thermal zone of the reactor, where the biochar is accumulated, forming a bed that grows as more biomass is fed and pyrolyzed. The pyrolysis vapours leave the reactor from its bottom part passing through a condensation system composed of a series of four glass condensers immersed in an ice bath, where the liquid bio-oil is collected. The non-condensable gases are measured by a volumetric gas meter and then accumulated in gas sampling bags for further analysis. During the catalytic experiments, the vapours pass through the catalytic bed, placed in the isothermal section of the catalytic furnace. The bio-oil samples were taken every hour by using two parallel series of condensers (the reactor outlet was sent to the second series so the first one could be retrieved). Non-condensable gases were collected every 20 minutes by switching sampling bags, so the hourly results for the gas fraction were calculated as the cumulative of three gas samples. The total duration of the tests in the continuous reaction system was 4 h.

In the case of the batch experiments, the screw feeder is replaced by a feeding tank, in which 5 g of biomass are discharged at once through a ball valve. The bio-oil condensation system is the same as that used in the continuous configuration, while the gases are now accumulated in a totalizer. The nitrogen flow is kept for 30 min to achieve the complete pyrolysis of the feedstock and to ensure that all vapours and gases were collected. More detailed information about this system can be found elsewhere [24–26].

Both pyrolysis configurations were tested under atmospheric pressure at two different temperatures of the thermal section, 350 and 500 °C, while the temperature of the catalytic section was kept at 450 °C in all cases. The temperature was chosen based on the results obtained in a previous work [24], in which 450 °C was established as the optimal temperature for the n-ZSM-5 activity. The zeolite loading used in both cases was 3 g, with a particle size in the range of 180-250 µm to minimize pressure drops and mass transfer limitations.

Fig. 1. Schematics of the continuous (A) and batch (B) catalytic pyrolysis systems.

2.2. Biomass feedstock and pyrolysis products characterization

Oak tree (*Quercus Robur*) woodchips, supplied by Ence (Spain), were used as feedstock for the pyrolysis experiments as representative forest residue because of their high homogeneity and low ash content. They were grounded and sieved to a particle size of 0.5 – 1 mm and then oven-dried at 90 °C for 48 h before each analysis and pyrolysis test.

Biomass proximate analysis was performed according to the latest European standards. Moisture was determined by weighting the sample after oven-dried at 105 °C for 12 h (UNE-EN ISO 18134-1:2016) while the volatile matter was determined by thermogravimetric analysis heating the sample to 900 °C with a rate of 10 °C/min and 80 ml/min of Ar, using a Netzsch STA-449-F3 instrument equipped with a SiC furnace (UNE-EN ISO 18123:2016). The ash content was determined by burning 5 g of dry sample in a muffle oven at 550 °C, under static air conditions for 30 min (UNE-EN ISO 18122:2016). The fixed carbon percentage was calculated by difference. Ash chemical composition was determined by ICP-OES analysis using a Pelkin-Elmer Optima 7300-DV instrument. Before the analysis, the ash sample was digested in a mixture of HF and HNO₃ under microwave heating radiation using an Anton Paar MW3000 microwave. An elemental screening was performed based on the most common elements present in lignocellulosic residues [8], while Si content was calculated by difference [27,28]. Moreover, the biopolymer distribution of the biomass used as feedstock was established using a procedure adapted from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), which is described in the literature [29]. C, H, N, and S contents of the biomass, biochar, coke and bio-oil samples were determined by elemental analysis using ThermoScientific Flash 2000 equipment, while O content was calculated by difference.

The bio-oil water content was obtained by Karl-fisher titration using a Mettler-Toledo V20-S equipment. Both bio-oil yield and composition are provided on a water-free basis (denoting it as bio-oil*). The water production in catalytic experiments was high enough to provoke the

segregation of the liquid product in both aqueous and organic phases. In these cases, the two phases were separated manually after centrifugation, weighted and analysed individually. However, bio-oil* results are presented as the weighted sum of the organic fraction present in both phases, so that they can be compared to the single-phase bio-oils obtained in non-catalytic experiments.

Bio-oil* chemical composition was determined by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) using an Agilent 8860 GC-5977B GC/MSD instrument equipped with a fused silica HP5-MS UI column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 mm). The NIST 2017 library was used for the identification of compounds with a minimum matching factor of 85/100. The main compounds (those with a relative peak area higher than 1%) were quantified according to the internal standard calibration method, using dioxane as solvent and cyclohexanol as the internal standard. The identified compounds were grouped into the following families, regarding their main functional groups: ketones, ethers and esters (KET, ETH & EST), carboxylic acids (AC), aromatics (AR), furans (FUR), oxygenated aromatics (O-AR), and sugars (SUG). An average response factor was calculated for each family and applied to minority compounds to estimate their concentration. This method allows the definition of a new parameter denoted as “bio-oil* GC-MS detected fraction”, which is calculated as the sum of the mass concentration of all identified compounds [25,26] and represents the share of bio-oil compounds that can be detected by this technique regarding the overall bio-oil* yield. The non-detected components are mostly oligomeric molecules from the incomplete decomposition of lignocellulose bio-polymers.

The yield of the coke deposited on the catalyst was estimated by combustion in a Netzsch STA-449-F3 instrument, heating the sample to 900 °C with a rate of 10 °C/min under 80 ml/min of synthetic air.

The composition of the gaseous product was determined by micro-GC analysis, using an Agilent 490 instrument equipped with two columns, a CP-MolSieve 5 Å and a P-PoraPLOT Q, and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). The following gaseous molecules were quantified: H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆, C₃H₈, C₄H₈, and C₄H₁₀.

Finally, the HHV of both biomass and pyrolysis products was calculated according to Eq. (1), valid for solid, liquid, and gaseous fuels [30]:

$$HHV \left(\frac{MJ}{kg} \right) = 0.349 \cdot C + 1.178 \cdot H + 0.101 \cdot S - 0.103 \cdot O - 0.015 \cdot N - 0.021 \cdot Ash \quad (1)$$

where C, H, O, N, S, and Ash are expressed in wt% on a dry basis.

The overall mass balance was calculated from the total weight of the products collected at the end of each experiment and, in all cases, it was closed with an experimental error lower than 5 % referred to the total amount of biomass fed. Then, the yields of the different pyrolysis products were calculated according to Eq. (2):

$$Mass\ yield_i (wt.\ %) = \frac{Mass_i (g)}{Total\ biomass (g)} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

Where i = gas, water, bio-oil*, biochar, and coke.

Both yields and compositions of the pyrolysis products in the batch experiments have been compared to those obtained in the first hour of the time-on-stream (TOS) in the continuous configuration, so that the total amount of processed biomass is the same (5 g and 5 g/h, respectively). In the case of the CM reactor, the 1 h TOS yields were evaluated considering the products collected and the biomass fed during 1 h. The gas fraction was collected and analysed every 20 min and its hourly gas yield was calculated as the cumulative value of three gas samples.

2.3. Catalyst characterization

A commercial nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite provided by Clariant, Switzerland (n-ZSM-5, [Si/Al]_{MOL}=42) was used as a catalyst for the catalytic pyrolysis experiments. The aluminium content was determined by ICP-OES analysis in a Pelkin-Elmer Optima 7300-DV instrument. The crystallinity of this sample was evaluated by X-ray diffraction technique using a Philips PW 3040/00 MPD/MRD diffractometer (45 kV, 40mA), while the average crystal size was estimated by transmission electronic microscopy (TEM) with a Philips TECNAI 20 instrument (200 kV). The textural properties were determined by argon adsorption-desorption isotherms at 87 K in a Micromeritics 3Flex analyzer, degassing the sample at 300 °C under vacuum for 3 h before the analysis. The surface area was estimated with the BET equation, while the *t-plot* method was used to calculate the micropores and the mesopore-external surface areas. The total pore volume was calculated at a relative pressure value of 0.97. The concentration of the Brønsted and Lewis acid sites was determined by pyridine adsorption coupled with FT-IR analysis using a Jasco-4600 spectrometer equipped with a TGS detector. The catalyst sample was shaped into a wafer (15 mg/cm²) and it was activated at 525 °C for 4 h under vacuum. Then, the pyridine absorption took place at 150 °C for 20 min, which was fed by a house-made vaporization system. The desorption process was run at 150, 250, 350 and 450 °C with 20 min of isotherm conditions between each step. The FT-IR spectra were recorded at the end of every isotherm, and the concentration of the Brønsted and Lewis acid sites were calculated using extinction coefficients ($\xi_{\text{BAS}} = 1.09 \text{ cm}\cdot\mu\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $\xi_{\text{LAS}} = 1.71 \text{ cm}\cdot\mu\text{mol}^{-1}$) from the literature [31].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Feedstock and catalyst characterization

Table 1 summarizes both proximate and ultimate analyses of the oak woodchips used as feedstock, as well as the ash composition and the biopolymers distribution. The dry feedstock presents a high content of volatile matter (81.7 wt%), which agrees well with its holocellulose

content. The ash content in this biomass is low, although it is rich in alkali and alkaline earth metals, mainly Ca and K, which will be concentrated in the biochar fraction during the pyrolysis process. These metals may present significant catalytic activity and can interact with pyrolysis vapours, promoting both cracking and carbonization reactions and reducing the bio-oil yield [28,32,33]. The oxygen concentration in the oak woodchips is quite significant, which leads to a low HHV, about half of the usual values of fossil fuels.

Table 1. Proximate and ultimate analyses, biopolymers and ash composition of oak tree woodchips.

Proximate analysis, db ¹ (wt%)					Ash composition	
Ash	Volatile matter		Fixed carbon		(mg/Kg _{biomass})	
1.8	81.7		16.5		Ca	1414.0
Ultimate analysis, daf ² (wt%)					K	1223.0
C	H	N	O	HHV (MJ/kg)	Mg	19.3
50.6	6.1	0.1	43.2	19.51	Mn	12.3
Biopolymers distribution (wt%)					P	10.5
Cellulose		Hemicellulose		Lignin	Na	7.0
48.9		19.5		31.6	Fe	1.8
					Si	14810.0

¹ db: dry basis; ² daf: dry and ash-free basis.

The XRD pattern of the n-ZSM-5 sample is shown in Fig. S1, denoting that it is a highly crystalline zeolite with MFI topology. The TEM images (Fig. S2) confirm the presence of nano-sized crystals in the range of 20 – 50 nm, which tend to form aggregates of 20 – 50 μ m. The textural and acidic properties of the n-ZSM-5 sample are summarized in Table 2. As observed, this sample exhibits both a high micro-porosity and a significant contribution of the external surface area as a consequence of the nanometric size of its crystals. The external surface area enhances the conversion of bulky molecules present in the pyrolysis vapours into lighter, valuable products. On the other hand, the n-ZSM-5 catalyst presents a relatively high concentration of Brønsted acid sites, which are reported to be the major responsible for the catalytic activity of the zeolites in the transformation of pyrolysis bio-oils, although the Lewis acid sites may also contribute to the catalytic pyrolysis transformations [34].

Table 2. Textural and acidic properties of the n-ZSM-5 catalyst.

Si/Al ^a	S _{BET} ^b (m ² g ⁻¹)	S _{EXT} ^b (m ² g ⁻¹)	S _{MIC} ^b (m ² g ⁻¹)	V _T ^b (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V _{MIC} ^b (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	C _{BRØNSTED} ^c (mmol g ⁻¹)	C _{LEWIS} ^c (mmol g ⁻¹)
42	392	117	275	0.515	0.176	0.205	0.091

^aQuantities in molar ratio; ^b Ar physisorption at 87 K; ^c Pyridine desorption-FTIR (150 °C).

3.2. Batch vs continuous biomass feeding modes in thermal pyrolysis

In this work, pyrolysis of biomass using batch and continuous feeding modes (BM and CM, respectively) of the feedstock have been investigated, and the two operation modes have been compared using the same type of reactor but changing the feeding system. The comparison has been performed for the same amount of biomass in both cases (5 g). Moreover, the thermal pyrolysis experiments were run at two different temperatures, 350 and 500 °C, to study the differences between the two operation configurations in the absence of any external catalyst.

The mass yields of the pyrolysis products as well as those of the gaseous components are shown in Fig. 2-A and B, respectively, with error bars indicating the high level of reliability and precision in the experimental data reported. As observed, the bio-oil* fraction (in water-free basis) is the major product in all thermal experiments with yields higher than 35 wt%. This fact could be associated with the high particle heating rate achieved in both configurations, which maximizes the production of the organic liquid phase [35].

When the temperature is raised from 350 to 500 °C, the same variations are observed for both operation modes in terms of product distribution. Less biochar and more gases are produced due to the enhanced depolymerization of the lignocellulose biopolymers while the generation of gases increases due to the promotion of cracking reactions with the temperature. Consequently, the yields of the bio-oil* and water increase, in accordance with the literature [24,36,37].

Regarding the differences between the two operation systems, less biochar is produced in the CM system at both temperatures studied, indicating that the volatilization of the biomass is

more efficient. This is reflected in the gas yield, which is almost double in the experiments operating in continuous mode. The bio-oil* yield is approximately 36 wt% for both systems at 350 °C, while at 500 °C it is slightly higher in the CM reactor compared to the BM one, with values of c.a. 45 and 40 wt%, respectively. In addition, the autocatalytic effect of the biochar should be also considered since this fraction may promote cracking and carbonization reactions, especially at 500 °C, as demonstrated in a previous work [38]. Thus, the higher bio-oil* yield of the CM system with respect to the BM one could also be related to the presence of a smaller biochar bed. The yield of the different gaseous components (Fig. 2-B) is higher in the CM system in agreement with the higher overall gas production. The main gas components are CO₂ and CO in all experiments, which are produced from decarboxylation and decarbonylation reactions, respectively. However, a significant increase in CO production can be observed in the CM configuration. Other minority gases include light paraffins (LP) and olefins (LO), whose production is also favoured in the CM system regarding the BM one. The water yield is lower in the CM reactor, indicating that the dehydration of condensable components of the pyrolysis vapours is less favoured when feeding the biomass in continuous way. Also, this effect can be related to the lower biochar yield obtained in the continuous configuration, since this operating mode could reduce the re-polymerization of dehydrated anhydrous sugars resulting from holocellulose decomposition, leading to a lower production of additional biochar and water [8,39].

Fig. 2. Products yield (A) and gas composition (B) from thermal pyrolysis of oak, at two different temperatures (500 and 350 °C), using a batch mode (BM) and a continuous mode (CM) reactor. The results of the CM reactor are referred to 1 h TOS.

The molecular composition of the bio-oil* is one of the most important aspects to establish the potential applications of the product as well as the design of downstream processes to produce biofuels or bio-based chemicals. Fig. 3-A illustrates the molecular composition in terms of mass yields determined from calibrated GC-MS analyses of the bio-oils* obtained operating in both batch and continuous biomass feeding modes. In general, SUG, O-AR and AC are the three major families, followed by FUR and KET, ETH & EST, whose generation can be associated with the primary decomposition of the three biopolymers present in the biomass (SUG from cellulose, FUR from hemicellulose, O-AR and AC from lignin) [8] as well as with the occurrence of secondary reactions within the different organic components present in the pyrolysis vapours. The most

representative compounds of each family are levoglucosan, syringol, acetic acid, furfural, cyclopentenone and hydroxybutanone, respectively, as shown in Table S1. As described in the experimental section, the bio-oil* GC-MS detected fraction can be considered a parameter to assess the quality of the bio-oil* as it represents the share of light components in the bio-oil* coming from the conversion of lignocellulose oligomers and heavy compounds. Fig. 3-B depicts the yields of both GC-MS detected and non-detected fractions of the bio-oils obtained in both operating configurations.

As expected, the composition of the bio-oil* fraction is strongly affected by temperature. Thus, higher yields of AC and lower ones of KET, ETH & EST are observed at 500 °C, while the tendency of FUR depends on the operation mode. As to SUG and O-AR, the CM configuration displays remarkable differences when working at different temperatures, favouring their formation at 500 °C. At 350 °C non-significant differences can be found in the yield of both GC-MS detected and non-detected fractions, showing values of about 22 and 15 wt%, respectively, for both systems. At higher temperatures, the share of the detected fraction is also similar for both operating modes, although an increase of c.a. 7 – 9 wt% takes place in the yield of the non-visible fraction. This fact denotes that higher temperatures enhance the volatilization of the biomass, increasing the bio-oil yield, although the resultant volatile components are of high molecular weight and, therefore, not detected by GC-MS. Those non-detectable molecules are not released as vapours at 350 °C, becoming part of the biochar fraction instead. These results evidence that a thermal process is insufficient to obtain a handling valuable liquid.

The variations in the yield of SUG in the pyrolysis tests resemble those observed in the total bio-oil* yield, showing similar values at 350 °C in both reaction modes, and a higher SUG yield in the CM system (c.a. 6.9 wt%) at 500 °C. The yields of O-AR and KET, ETH & EST are also higher in the CM configuration, while AC production is remarkably lower than in the BM assays at both temperatures studied. These tendencies can be linked to the balance between the enhanced

conversion of the biopolymers achieved in the CM configuration, yielding SUG, FUR and O-AR, and the cracking reactions producing light oxygenated compounds, which are also easily converted into gases. This is particularly evident for the SUG and FUR yields obtained at 500 °C, the latter being a direct product of the dehydration of sugars. On the contrary, the variations observed in the yield of AC and KET, ETH & EST cannot be related to a particular family of compounds since they can be produced from both the direct degradation of the three lignocellulose biopolymers [40,41] as well as the secondary reactions occurring within the vapours stream, e.g. de-alkylation of highly substituted phenols and deoxygenation of sugars followed by ring scission and rearrangement reactions, where furans are intermediate products [42,43]. It is also possible to produce esters from carboxylic acids through hydrogenolysis, C=O hydrogenation and reaction with another carboxylic acid [44]. This fact can be observed in Table S1, where a different distribution of KET, ETH & EST is obtained depending on the operation mode. Thus, the formation of acetic acid derivatives (acetyloxy-acetic acid and glycolic acid-ethyl ester) is detected, which could partially explain the lower AC and the higher KET, ETH & EST yields when shifting from batch to continuous pyrolysis.

Fig. 3 Bio-oil* GC-MS molecular analysis (A) and GC-MS detected yield (B), from thermal pyrolysis of oak, at two different temperatures (500 and 350 °C), using a batch mode (BM) and a continuous mode (CM) reactor. The results of the CM reactor are referred to 1 h TOS.

The elemental composition of both the bio-oil* and biochar fractions from thermal pyrolysis experiments is shown in Table 3. The bio-oil* oxygen content is very high, ranging from 34 to 40 wt%, being responsible for the high instability and the low HHV of this liquid product. The bio-oil* with the highest HHV is obtained in the CM operating at 500 °C, which exhibits C and O contents of c.a. 58 and 34 wt%, respectively. On the other hand, the biochar obtained in the CM configuration presents a higher C content than that of the BM one, showing higher differences at 500 °C. Hence, the biochar produced in the CM reactor at 500 °C exhibits O and C contents of <5 wt% and >90 wt%, respectively, while the biochar produced in the BM system reaches an O content of c.a. 12 wt% and a carbon content of c.a. 85 wt%. This low oxygen content in the

biochar produced in the continuous reactor at 500 °C suggests that, under these conditions, it is drastically deoxygenated. This result agrees well with the FT-IR analysis of this fraction published in a previous study, where a number of biochar samples were produced at different pyrolysis temperatures, showing very low oxygen content for temperatures above 500 °C [38].

Table 3. Bio-oil* and biochar elemental composition, from thermal pyrolysis of oak at two different temperatures (500 and 350 °C), in batch mode (BM) and continuous mode (CM) reactors.

		C (wt%)	H (wt%)	N (wt%)	O (wt%)	HHV (MJ/kg)
Bio-oil* (daf ¹)	BM 500 °C	52.1	6.6	0.5	40.9	21.7
	CM 500 °C	58.0	6.8	0.6	34.6	24.6
	BM 350 °C	54.4	6.4	0.6	38.5	22.6
	CM 350 °C	52.5	6.3	0.8	40.4	21.6
Biochar (daf ¹)	BM 500 °C	85.0	3.0	0.3	11.7	30.3
	CM 500 °C	92.1	3.3	0.3	4.3	32.1
	BM 350 °C	76.9	3.9	0.3	19.0	28.2
	CM 350 °C	79.9	3.7	0.3	16.1	29.2

¹ daf: dry and ash-free basis

The differences between the two systems are less pronounced at 350 °C compared to 500 °C. However, the divergence between gas, water and biochar yields can still be appreciated at the lowest temperature. The CM system feeds a lower amount of biomass per unit of time and, therefore, the biomass particle heating rate is higher, favouring the biopolymers' cleavage and increasing both gas and bio-oil* yields, especially at 500 °C. Consequently, the partial pressure of the generated vapours is lower in comparison to the BM reactor. Both the heating rate and the vapours partial pressure contribute to the lower biochar and water yields, as well as the higher gas production, especially CO. The latter can be released from the direct deoxygenation of the methoxy functional groups of the lignin structure, which then condense to form the aromatic structure of the biochar [45], showing a very low oxygen content. The reduction observed in the biochar yield due to the lower partial pressure of the pyrolysis vapours in the CM mode agrees well with a recent experimental study about oak pyrolysis under moderate

pressure by F. Artillo et al. [46], in which they found that a high pressure promotes the biochar production at the expenses of the bio-oil* fraction.

Another parameter that may affect the distribution of the pyrolysis products is the residence time of gases/vapours in the reactor. Monitoring the volumetric flow of the gases in the BM system it was estimated that the biomass amount (5 g), loaded at once in the reactor, is completely converted in 4 min. As a result, it is estimated that the residence time of gases/vapours in the BM system is several times lower than in the CM one, although the concentration of those products is quite higher in the former one (about 4 times higher in the BM versus the CM, which has been estimated considering the average amount of pyrolysis products generated per unit of time in each case). Both residence time and concentration are key parameters influencing the pyrolysis kinetics in opposite directions, which may also depend on the reaction order of the different chemical transformations occurring during the pyrolysis process [47,48]. In overall, from the results above described, it can be concluded that the higher gases/vapour concentration in the BM system compensate the lower residence time, thus favouring the formation of secondary char and water in comparison with the CM configuration. In the same way, it can be envisaged that working under high volatile concentrations (BM) favour dehydration reactions through bimolecular transformations, whereas decarbonylation reactions, involving just one single molecule, occur in a higher extension under low concentration conditions (CM). Likewise, the high production of acids could be influenced by the high vapours partial pressure in the BM system, promoting their formation from sugars and lignin fragments, whereas the low residence time prevents the further acids conversion.

3.3. Batch vs Continuous Mode in catalytic pyrolysis

Both the BM and CM pyrolysis systems have been tested for the catalytic pyrolysis of oak woodchips using a commercial nanosized ZSM-5 as a catalyst, and have been compared in terms of product yields, bio-oil* deoxygenation degree and production of aromatic hydrocarbons. The

temperature of the pyrolysis zone was set at 350 and 500 °C, while the temperature was kept at 450 °C in the catalytic zone. Also, in this case, the comparison between both configurations has been performed for the same amount of biomass (5 g) and also the same catalyst loading.

The pyrolysis product distribution and the gas composition are shown in Fig. 4-A and C, respectively, while the difference in the yields of the catalytic test in comparison with the thermal experiments is represented in Fig. 4-B and D. As observed, the bio-oil* production is lower in the catalytic experiments, while both gas and water productions are significantly increased with respect to the thermal assays. This is due to the increased cracking and dehydration reactions promoted by the n-ZSM-5 zeolite, in addition to the formation of coke on the catalyst surface. The biochar yield remains unchanged since it is only affected by the temperature of the thermal zone. In the catalytic experiments performed at 350 °C, the bio-oil* yield is the same when using both BM and CM configurations, reaching a value of c.a. 15 wt%. At 500 °C the bio-oil* yield is lower in the continuous system, passing from 45.0 wt% in the thermal experiment to 16.7 wt%. This remarkable reduction can be mainly related to the production of water, CO and CO₂. Despite the water yield of the BM system being higher than the CM ones, it is worth noting that, operating in a continuous mode, both catalytic experiments produce more water and CO in comparison to their respective thermal assays (Fig. 4-B and C). On the other hand, the production of LO and LP is higher in the CM reactor. These results could be related to the lower amount of biomass fed per unit of time in the CM mode, which improves the catalytic conversion of the volatiles components in the bio-oil* fraction due to a longer residence time in the catalytic bed. In contrast, in the case of the BM configuration, the biomass is thermally decomposed in a quite shorter period of time, hence the generated gases/vapours pass through the catalyst bed with quite higher concentrations, leading to an enhanced deposition of coke over the catalyst's surface and, therefore, decreasing its cracking activity.

Fig. 4. Product yields from catalytic pyrolysis of oak (A) and difference with the thermal experiment (B). Gas composition from catalytic pyrolysis (C) and difference with the thermal experiment (D), at two different temperatures (500 and 350 °C), using a batch mode (BM) and a continuous mode (CM) reactor. The results of the CM reactor are referred to 1 h TOS.

The molecular composition of the bio-oils* resulting from the catalytic pyrolysis of oak woodchips and their differences with the thermal reactions are shown in Fig. 5-A and B, respectively. As can be seen, the main organic family in catalytic bio-oils* corresponds to aromatic hydrocarbons (AR) with yields ranging between 6 and 8 wt%, while they are practically absent in thermal bio-oils. This result is assigned to the high aromatization activity of the n-ZSM-5 zeolite, which is capable of producing aromatic hydrocarbons from sugars, furans (which disappear in the catalytic bio-oil*) and olefins present in the pyrolysis vapours via subsequent decarbonylation, oligomerization and aromatization processes or Diels-Alder condensation reactions [15]. The shape selectivity of the n-ZSM-5 allows the production of xylene, which is the

main component of the AR family as shown in Table S2, along with significant amounts of toluene, ethylbenzene, dimethyl-indene, and methyl-naphthalene. The production of AR compounds is higher in the CM reactor at both temperatures studied. This is due to the higher production of FUR (at 350 °C), SUG and olefins (at 350 and 500 °C), but also to the lower coke formation. Thus, the high concentration of gases/vapours contacting with the catalyst in the BM reactor could negatively affect the selectivity of valuable products as it favours the formation of coke [49]. The higher coke formation is also consistent with the favoured production of O-AR in the BM system, since they are reported to be the main coke precursors [50]. Thus, the production of methyl-benzofuran in the BM reactor is 3.5 times higher than the obtained for the CM configuration (Table S2). This fact could explain the small increase in the O-AR yield during BM catalytic pyrolysis. The main component of the O-AR family in the thermal assays is syringol (Table S1) while in the catalytic experiments is cresol (Table S2), which can be obtained from the former via demethoxylation and decarbonylation reactions promoted by the zeolite [45]. Additionally, the yield of AC and KET, ETH & EST is very low in all cases, probably because they are easily converted into gases by the catalyst.

In general, a lower temperature in the thermal zone is beneficial for the AR production in both configurations, since the share of SUG and FUR increases with respect to the O-AR family. This allowed to reach a maximum yield of c.a. 8 wt% for AR compounds, at 350 °C in the CM system.

The catalytic promotion of cracking reactions by the zeolite reduces the total bio-oil* yield, but affecting in a more extension to the heavy components (GC-MS non-detected species) more than to the lighter fraction (Fig. 5-C and D). Hence, the zeolite improves the bio-oil* quality not only in terms of production of aromatic compounds, but also through the conversion of lignocellulose oligomers into lighter molecules.

Fig. 5. Bio-oil* GC-MS molecular analysis (A) and difference with the thermal experiment (B). GC-MS detected yield (C) and difference with the thermal experiment (D), at two different temperatures (500 and 350 °C), using a batch mode (BM) and a continuous mode (CM) reactor. The results of the CM reactor are referred to 1 h TOS.

The bio-oil* and coke elemental analysis from the catalytic experiments are shown in Table 4. As expected, the promotion of deoxygenation and aromatization reactions leads to an important reduction in the oxygen content of the bio-oil*, passing from 34.6 – 40.9 wt% in thermal experiments to 9.3 – 10.9 wt% in the catalytic ones. The low O content of the bio-oil* results in an improved HHV with respect to the thermal pyrolysis, approaching that of traditional fossil fuels which are in the range of 40-50 MJ/kg [51]. The best results are obtained in the CM system at 350 °C. This is reflected in the Van Krevelen diagram (Fig. S3) since the bio-oil* from the CM catalytic pyrolysis shows higher H/C and lower O/C ratios than the BM system, indicating a higher quality as a fuel due to the higher AR and the lower O-AR yields. However, it seems that

the zeolite incorporation attenuates the differences between both operating modes since small variations can be appreciated in the C and O contents of the bio-oil*.

On the contrary, remarkable differences can be observed in the elemental analysis of the coke fraction. The formation of coke is due to the condensation, oligomerization and polymerization of the pyrolysis vapours, catalysed by the acidic sites of the zeolite. Although the major coke precursors are lignin-derived O-AR compounds, also olefins and AR can contribute to the coke formation [50]. In fact, the coke generated in the continuous catalytic pyrolysis assays shows higher C and lower O contents than the BM ones, suggesting that their precursors are AR compounds more than O-AR. This result is consistent with a recent work published by Gancedo et al. [52], in which they found that furan derivatives can generate oxygenated coke if they condense to form benzofurans, which are mainly produced in the BM system as mentioned before. On the other hand, graphite-type coke can be formed by polycyclic aromatic compounds, contributing to the coke formation mainly in the CM reactor.

Table 4. Bio-oil* and coke elemental composition, from catalytic pyrolysis of oak at two different temperatures (500 and 350 °C), in batch mode (BM) and continuous mode (CM) reactors.

		C (wt%)	H (wt%)	N (wt%)	O (wt%)	HHV (MJ/kg)
Bio-oil* (daf ¹)	BM 500 °C	79.8	8.9	0.4	10.9	37.2
	CM 500 °C	81.6	7.9	0.5	10.0	36.7
	BM 350 °C	79.2	7.2	0.0	13.6	34.7
	CM 350 °C	83.3	7.4	0.0	9.3	36.9
Coke (daf ¹)	BM 500 °C	75.2	5.4	0.0	19.4	-
	CM 500 °C	89.0	4.4	0.1	6.5	-
	BM 350 °C	79.9	5.3	0.0	14.8	-
	CM 350 °C	87.2	4.2	0.0	8.7	-

¹ daf: dry and ash-free basis

4. Conclusions

The distribution and composition of the products of thermal and catalytic fast-pyrolysis of lignocellulose is strongly influenced by the biomass feeding mode. During thermal pyrolysis, the switch from batch to continuous feeding of biomass lead to a faster and more efficient pyrolysis, producing less biochar, less water, and more gases at both temperatures studied (350 and 500 °C). The bio-oil* (bio-oil in water-free basis) yield is practically the same for both configurations (c.a. 36 wt%) when working at 350 °C but it increases in the continuous system at 500 °C, reaching a value of c.a. 45 wt%. These variations can be assigned to the enhanced volatilization of the organic components in continuous mode, which avoids the occurrence of secondary charring and condensation reactions. Thus, in the batch mode the biomass pyrolysis is completed in about 4 min, while in the continuous system the same amount of feedstock is fed and pyrolyzed during one hour. This results in a higher heating rate and a lower partial pressure of the vapours inside the reactor volume for the continuous system.

Moreover, the increased volatilization of bio-oil* components and the longer residence times in the continuous mode allows obtaining a liquid fraction richer in SUG and O-AR compounds coming from the direct decomposition of the lignocellulose biopolymers, as well as with a higher concentration of KET, ETH & EST due to the conversion of AC. Additionally, the biochar produced in the continuous mode is strongly deoxygenated with respect to the batch one. Since little differences are observed in the bio-oil* O content, the high biochar deoxygenation degree of the continuous system can be linked to the remarkable increase in the yield of CO, generated from the direct deoxygenation of the lignin methoxy functional groups during biochar formation.

When the n-ZSM-5 is introduced into the reactor catalyst zone, the different operation modes affect the way in which the vapours enter into contact with the catalyst. In the batch mode, the gases and vapours formed in the thermal pyrolysis zone reach the catalyst bed with a high concentration whereas in the continuous system it occurs progressively, affording a more

efficient catalytic conversion. As a consequence, the amount of coke deposited over the n-ZSM-5 catalyst is significantly lower for the continuous system, attenuating its deactivation. This fact has also an important effect on the bio-oil* composition, showing a higher share of light components and an enhanced yield of aromatic hydrocarbons when using the continuous reaction system. The high coke formation of the BM system is attributed to a higher interaction between the catalyst and O-AR compounds, as well as to the presence of furans derivatives (benzofurans) in the bio-oil*. The latter are not converted further to AR compounds by the catalyst and contribute to coke formation instead, in contrast with the CM system where the yield of benzofurans is 3.5 times lower.

Acknowledgments

The present work received funding from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation under the grant PID2020-114740RB-C21 (AdBioCaP Project).

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